

DISABILITY AND INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES (PWD) ENROLLMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN INDIA

Dr. SINDHU. K

Associate Professor, Department of Economics, The Cochin College, Kochi-2, Kerala, India.

Email: sindhuk@thecochoincollege.edu.in, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8548-2134>

Dr. R. SANTHOSH

Professor, Department of Economics, Government Law College, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India.

Email: santhoshreco@gmail.com, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-5077-3549>

Dr. N. KARUNAKARAN *

Principal, People Institute of Management Studies (PIMS), Munnad-Post, Chengala (Via), Kasaragod, Kerala, India. *Corresponding Author Email: narankarun@gmail.com,

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7213-2841>

SALINI. J S

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, NSS College, Pandalam, Kerala, India.

Email: salinijs@gmail.com, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3939-4075>

Abstract

This research investigates enrollment trends of Persons with Disabilities (PWD) in Indian higher education institutions, with a particular focus on the implications of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act, 2016. Drawing on data from the All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) for the period 2012-13 to 2021-22, the study examines patterns of enrollment growth, gender disparities, and regional variations. The results reveal modest overall growth in PWD enrollment, ongoing gender imbalances, and pronounced regional disparities, highlighting Kerala as a model for inclusive educational practices. Policy recommendations include the enhancement of gender-inclusive strategies, mitigation of socio-economic barriers, and the strengthening of post-pandemic recovery initiatives in higher education for PWD.

Keywords: Disability, Higher Education, PWD Enrollment, Gender Disparities, RPWD Act, Inclusive Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Disability constitutes a complex, multidimensional issue that perpetuates socio-economic inequalities and exclusion. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 1.3 billion individuals globally experience significant disabilities, accounting for 16% of the world's population. Despite their prevalence, persons with disabilities (PWD) often remain marginalized, with limited visibility and access to fundamental rights across many societies. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development underscores the importance of PWD inclusion, with seven out of the 169 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) explicitly addressing disability-related issues. A key advancement in disability rights is the adoption of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), which marked a paradigm shift from the medical model to a human rights-based approach.

The CRPD conceptualizes disability as the result of interactions between individuals' impairments and societal barriers. This framework informs the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act, 2016, in India, which seeks to promote equal opportunities for PWD, particularly in the field of education.

India's Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act, 2016, represents a pivotal advancement in promoting disability inclusion, aligning with the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) to empower persons with disabilities (PWD) in the realm of education. The Act defines critical concepts such as "persons with benchmark disabilities" and delineates key disability categories. It mandates the implementation of inclusive education policies, including the provision of accessible infrastructure, examination accommodations, and a 5% reservation of seats for PWD in government higher education institutions. Existing literature highlights a persistent gap in PWD enrollment in higher education, both globally and within India (Ghara, T. K., 2021). While some studies have examined the legislative impacts, research on long-term trends related to gender and regional disparities in PWD enrollment remains limited. This study aims to address these gaps by analyzing data from the All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) over the past decade.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Following the adoption of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), numerous studies have been conducted globally to examine the trends and barriers to the inclusion of persons with disabilities (PWDs) in higher education. Mistry and Panigrahi (2023) has conducted a systematic literature search to identify studies on higher education for students with disabilities.

The primary search platform was Sodhganga, an Indian research repository, complemented by an additional internet search for relevant papers between April and June 2022. The search used specific keywords such as "higher education," "students with disabilities," "disabled students," "special educational needs," and "issues" or "problems" to gather relevant studies addressing the challenges and barriers faced by students with disabilities in higher education.

The research identifies that although several government initiatives such as disability reservations and financial support schemes have been established, the enrollment rate of Students with Disabilities (SWDs) in higher education remains significantly lower than expected. Key barriers identified include a lack of disability-friendly infrastructure, insufficient financial aid, and inadequate awareness among students and educators regarding disability provisions.

The study highlights that many higher education institutions fail to fully implement inclusive policies, contributing to the ongoing marginalization of SWDs. The authors recommend stricter enforcement of the RPWD Act, enhanced awareness campaigns, the establishment of disability units in universities, and increased financial and logistical support to ensure a more inclusive higher education environment for students with disabilities in India.

Amin et al. (2021) investigated the challenges faced by students with disabilities in higher education in Malaysia, revealing a significant disparity in access and inclusion compared to their non-disabled peers. Barriers such as inadequate physical infrastructure, limited access to assistive technologies, and a lack of awareness among faculty and peers were highlighted as major obstacles. These challenges hinder the effective inclusion of PWDs in higher education institutions. The study recommended the implementation of inclusive teaching strategies, greater faculty training, and comprehensive policy reforms as critical measures to foster a supportive environment for students with disabilities. The need for personalized learning approaches and increased sensitivity towards diverse learning needs was also emphasized as essential to reducing the inequities faced by PWDs in education.

Ghara (2021) examined the enrollment trends of PWD in Indian higher education from 2011 to 2020 using AISHE data. Despite government policies like the Higher Education for Persons with Special Needs (HEPSN) scheme and the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016, which mandate reservations and provisions for PWD students, the overall enrollment remains low across Indian states. The study highlighted significant gender disparities in PWD enrollment, and called for state-specific studies to address the lack of awareness and proper implementation of benefits for PWD students, emphasizing the need for more targeted interventions to improve inclusivity in higher education.

Vincent and Chiwandire (2019) examined the relationship between funding and inclusion in higher education, focusing on the historical challenges faced by students with disabilities due to limited public funding. Their comparative analysis of developed and developing countries, such as the UK, USA, Canada, Australia, South Africa, and India, revealed that while progressive funding models like disability scholarships have widened access, recent trends in funding cuts and the privatization of higher education threaten these advancements. Barriers such as bureaucratic application processes, restrictive testing methods, minimal financial support for part-time and distance learning, and inadequate day-to-day disability-related financial support persist. The study concluded that despite supportive policies, higher education institutions must urgently address these funding challenges to ensure equal access and academic success for students with disabilities.

In the context of Indonesia, Ajisuksmo (2017) found that the implementation of inclusive education in higher education faces numerous challenges. Despite efforts to provide equal access to students with disabilities, several barriers remain, including inadequate infrastructure, lack of specific university policies, insufficient budget allocations, and limited faculty awareness and training. While some progress has been made, such as the establishment of disability service centres, the majority of responsibility for addressing the needs of students with disabilities falls on individual faculties rather than being guided by comprehensive institutional policies. Stigma against students with disabilities, both from lecturers and fellow students persists, further complicating their inclusion. The study emphasized the need for improved infrastructure, policies, and staff training to create a more inclusive and supportive educational environment.

3. OBJECTIVES

This paper aims: (1) to analyze trends in the enrollment of Persons with Disabilities (PWD) in Indian higher education institutions from 2012-13 to 2021-22, (2) to evaluate the impact of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act, 2016, on the representation of PWD in higher education, (3) to examine gender disparities and identify the barriers affecting the enrollment of female PWD in higher education, and (4) to explore the correlation between overall enrollment growth and the inclusion of PWD in higher education institutions.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilizes data from the All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE), an annual data collection initiative conducted by the Ministry of Education, Government of India, to evaluate the status of higher education across the country. AISHE collects comprehensive data on various parameters, including student enrollment, faculty statistics, infrastructure, and financial aspects. Specifically, AISHE monitors the enrollment of marginalized groups, including Persons with Disabilities (PWD), offering valuable insights into trends related to gender, regional disparities, and the effectiveness of policies such as the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act. For this study, AISHE reports serve as a crucial data source for analyzing PWD inclusion in higher education. The analysis employs two primary indicators—PWD Enrollment Ratio and PWD Enrollment Gender Ratio—derived from AISHE data to evaluate the degree of inclusion and assess disparities in PWD enrollment.

The PWD Enrollment Ratio is a key metric that quantifies the percentage of Persons with Disabilities (PWD) enrolled in higher education relative to the total student enrollment. This ratio is instrumental in monitoring the inclusivity of educational institutions over time and evaluating the effectiveness of policies designed to enhance PWD participation in higher education. By tracking this ratio, researchers can assess trends in PWD enrollment and gauge the impact of legislative and institutional efforts aimed at improving access and opportunities for PWD students. The PWD Enrollment Gender Ratio is a metric that compares the number of female to male Persons with Disabilities (PWD) students in higher education. This ratio is essential for highlighting gender disparities within the PWD student population. By identifying differences in enrollment between female and male PWD students, the ratio helps in pinpointing specific barriers faced by female PWD students. This information is crucial for developing and implementing gender-inclusive policies aimed at promoting equal representation and addressing the unique challenges encountered by female PWD students. To examine regional disparities in the inclusion of Persons with Disabilities (PWD) in higher education, this study focuses on four representative states—Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, West Bengal, and Kerala. These states were selected due to their varied socio-economic conditions, providing a comprehensive perspective on regional differences in PWD enrollment and inclusion practices. As the most populous state in the northern region of India, Uttar Pradesh exemplifies challenges related to high population density and resource allocation, which may impact PWD inclusion in higher

education. Gujarat is a highly industrialized state that provides insights into the influence of economic development on PWD inclusion, reflecting how industrialization and economic growth can affect access to higher education for PWD. West Bengal is known for its rich educational traditions and cultural factors in the eastern region, West Bengal offers a perspective on how regional educational practices and cultural attitudes may affect PWD enrollment. Kerala is renowned for its progressive social policies and high literacy rates, Kerala serves as a benchmark for best practices in inclusive education and demonstrates effective strategies for promoting PWD participation. This selection of states offers a diverse and comprehensive view of how socio-economic factors and regional characteristics impact PWD enrollment in higher education across different parts of India.

5. RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the analysis of PWD enrollment in higher education institutions in India from 2012-13 to 2021-22. It discusses trends in overall PWD enrollment, gender disparities, and regional variations across four representative states—Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, West Bengal, and Kerala. The analysis is organized into three primary dimensions: (1) overall enrollment trends, (2) gender disparities, and (3) state-wise comparisons.

5.1. Overall PWD Enrollment Trends: The data indicates a gradual but consistent increase in the enrollment of Persons with Disabilities (PWD) in Indian higher education over the past decade. The PWD enrollment ratio, which measures the percentage of PWD students relative to the total student population, varied between 0.16% and 0.24% throughout this period. The lowest ratio of 0.16% was observed in 2013-14, while the highest ratio of 0.24% was recorded in 2019-20. Despite these incremental increases, the overall representation of PWD students in higher education remains substantially lower than anticipated.

Table 1: PWD Enrollment and Gender Ratio in Higher Education in India (2012-13 to 2021-22)

Year	Total Enrollment across all categories	Total PWD Enrollment	PWD Male Enrollment	PWD Female Enrollment	PWD Enrollment Ratio	PWD Enrollment Gender Ratio F/M
2012-13	30152417	54117	31547	22572	0.18	0.72
2013-14	32336234	51954	31374	20580	0.16	0.66
2014-15	34211637	64298	34757	29541	0.19	0.85
2015-16	34584781	74435	39718	34717	0.22	0.88
2016-17	35705905	70967	40894	30073	0.20	0.74
2017-18	36642378	74317	42630	31687	0.20	0.74
2018-19	37399388	85877	48212	37665	0.23	0.78
2019-20	38536359	92831	47830	45001	0.24	0.94
2020-21	41380713	79035	49334	29701	0.19	0.60
2021-22	43268181	88748	51373	37375	0.21	0.73

Source: Compiled from All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE), 2012-2022.

The enactment of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act, 2016, seems to have positively influenced PWD enrollment in higher education. A significant increase in enrollment is evident between 2014-15 and 2015-16, shortly following the implementation of the RPWD Act. This suggests that the legal framework contributed to creating a more favourable environment for enhancing PWD inclusion in higher education. The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020-21 seems to have resulted in a significant decrease in PWD enrollment, with the number of PWD students dropping from 92,831 in 2019-20 to 79,035 in 2020-21. This decline likely reflects the difficulties faced by PWD students during the pandemic, including challenges related to remote learning and access to resources. Although enrollment showed recovery in 2021-22, reaching 88,748 PWD students, it did not return to pre-pandemic levels. Over the decade from 2012-13 to 2021-22, the overall PWD enrollment growth rate has been positive, increasing from 54,117 students to 88,748, which represents a 64% increase. Nonetheless, this growth is modest relative to the overall expansion in higher education enrollment during the same period, highlighting that PWD students continue to be underrepresented in higher education.

5.2. Gender Disparities in PWD Enrollment: The PWD Enrollment Gender Ratio, which represents the proportion of female PWD students relative to male PWD students, reveals persistent gender imbalances throughout the study period. The ratio fluctuated between 0.60 and 0.94, consistently showing that male PWD students outnumber female PWD students. The highest gender ratio of 0.94 females per male was recorded in 2019-20, indicating near gender parity for that year. However, this improvement was short-lived, as the ratio sharply declined to 0.60 in 2020-21. This decline suggests a significant gender imbalance, likely exacerbated by the pandemic, which disproportionately affected female students due to socio-economic barriers, care giving responsibilities, and challenges in accessing technology. The lowest gender ratio of 0.60 occurred in 2020-21, with male PWD students significantly outnumbering female students. This substantial drop underscores the urgent need for targeted interventions to address the specific challenges faced by female PWD students, such as inadequate financial support, societal attitudes, and limited access to assistive technologies. Over the decade, the gender ratio for PWD students has consistently remained below 1.0, indicating that female PWD students are persistently underrepresented in higher education. This imbalance highlights the presence of structural barriers that disproportionately impact women with disabilities, thereby limiting their access to educational opportunities.

5.3. Comparison of PWD Enrollment Ratios in Higher Education (2012-2022): This section investigates the PWD enrollment ratio in higher education across India from 2012-13 to 2021-22. The enrollment ratio, indicating the percentage of PWD students relative to the total student population, is analyzed at both the national level and within four representative states: Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, West Bengal, and Kerala. This analysis provides insights into regional disparities and trends in the inclusion of PWD students in higher education, highlighting variations and patterns in enrollment across these diverse regions. A comparison of the PWD enrollment ratios across states reveals

notable regional disparities in the inclusion of PWD students in higher education. Kerala consistently exhibits the highest PWD enrollment ratios, ranging from 0.24% to 0.41%. This reflects the state’s robust policies, infrastructure, and public awareness efforts that promote inclusivity. Conversely, Uttar Pradesh experienced a significant peak in PWD enrollment in 2015-16, reaching 0.47%, but the ratio has since declined to 0.17% by 2021-22. This decline suggests fluctuations in the effectiveness and sustainability of policy implementation. Gujarat has consistently reported low PWD enrollment ratios, ranging from 0.11% to 0.19%, indicating ongoing challenges in fostering inclusivity within higher education. West Bengal has shown moderate improvement, with enrollment ratios fluctuating between 0.15% and 0.32%. The peak was observed in 2020-21, but the overall lack of consistency suggests variable effectiveness of inclusivity initiatives. These disparities underscore the differing effectiveness of policies and programs aimed at enhancing PWD inclusion across various regions of India.

Table 2: State-wise Comparison of PWD Enrollment Ratios in Higher Education (2012-2022)

Year	India	Uttar Pradesh	Gujarat	West Bengal	Kerala
2012-13	0.18	0.13	0.13	0.27	0.31
2013-14	0.16	0.19	0.12	0.19	0.25
2014-15	0.19	0.36	0.13	0.18	0.34
2015-16	0.22	0.47	0.11	0.16	0.34
2016-17	0.2	0.32	0.19	0.16	0.24
2017-18	0.2	0.26	0.13	0.23	0.25
2018-19	0.23	0.23	0.12	0.18	0.32
2019-20	0.24	0.28	0.15	0.17	0.33
2020-21	0.19	0.23	0.11	0.32	0.29
2021-22	0.21	0.17	0.28	0.15	0.41

Source: Compiled from All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE), 2012-2022.

Figure 1: State-wise Comparison of PWD Enrollment

Figure 1 illustrates the state-wise trends in PWD enrollment from 2012 to 2022 across four states: Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, West Bengal, and Kerala. Uttar Pradesh experienced noticeable fluctuations, with a significant peak in enrollment around 2015-16, followed by a dip and a rise again towards 2021-22. Gujarat shows a relatively stable trend with minor variations, maintaining lower enrollment levels throughout the period, except for a slight increase towards the end. West Bengal demonstrates a more consistent pattern, with small increases and decreases, but overall maintaining a steady range. Kerala, on the other hand, shows a clear upward trend, especially marked by a significant rise from 2020-21 to 2021-22, indicating growing PWD enrollment over the years.

The enactment of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act in 2016 appears to have influenced these trends in varying ways. Before 2016, Uttar Pradesh saw a sharp rise in enrollment, peaking in 2015-16. However, after the RPWD Act was introduced, the state's trend became more volatile, showing a decline post-2016 before rising again by 2021-22, though it did not reach previous peak levels.

Gujarat, meanwhile, exhibited a stable trend both before and after the Act, with only minor increases. West Bengal's consistent pattern throughout the period indicates that the RPWD Act had minimal impact on enrollment changes. In contrast, Kerala experienced significant growth in enrollment after 2016, especially from 2020-21 onward, suggesting that the RPWD Act may have had a more positive and direct influence on inclusion efforts in Kerala. Thus, while the RPWD Act contributed to a clearer upward trend in states like Kerala, its impact in other states varied, with some showing stability and others experiencing more fluctuations.

5.4. State-wise Comparison of Gender Ratios in PWD Enrollment (2012-2022): This section analyzes the gender ratio of Persons with Disabilities (PWD) enrolled in higher education across India and in specific states—Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, West Bengal, and Kerala—over the period from 2012-13 to 2021-22. The gender ratio is expressed as the number of female PWD students per male PWD student, providing insights into gender disparities in PWD enrollment across these regions.

Kerala and Uttar Pradesh exhibit notable variations in gender inclusivity within PWD enrollment. Kerala has consistently demonstrated strong gender inclusivity, with gender ratios ranging from 0.87 to 1.28 females per male across the period. The highest ratio of 1.28 in 2015-16 indicates that more females were enrolled than males that year. Kerala's gender ratio has remained close to parity in recent years, reflecting the state's robust policies and effective implementation of gender and disability inclusion measures.

Uttar Pradesh has also shown significant gender inclusivity, with a peak gender ratio of 1.53 in 2014-15, suggesting a higher enrollment of females compared to males in that year. Although the state has generally maintained a favourable gender ratio, it experienced a significant decline to 0.59 in 2020-21, highlighting challenges in sustaining gender inclusivity over time. These findings underscore the varying levels of

gender inclusivity in PWD enrollment across different states, with Kerala maintaining a relatively stable gender balance and Uttar Pradesh facing fluctuations.

Table 3: State-wise Comparison of Gender Ratios in PWD Enrollment (2012-2022)

Year	India	Uttar Pradesh	Gujarat	West Bengal	Kerala
2012-13	0.72	0.52	0.57	0.61	0.93
2013-14	0.66	0.71	0.52	0.43	0.62
2014-15	0.85	1.53	0.51	0.37	1.12
2015-16	0.87	1.31	0.53	0.45	1.28
2016-17	0.74	1.21	0.5	0.45	0.96
2017-18	0.74	0.95	0.69	0.74	0.98
2018-19	0.78	0.9	0.54	0.55	0.94
2019-20	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.49	0.88
2020-21	0.6	0.59	0.55	0.58	0.9
2021-22	0.73	0.97	0.75	0.53	0.87

Source: Compiled from All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE), 2012-2022.

In contrast, Gujarat and West Bengal have faced challenges in achieving gender balance in PWD enrollment: Gujarat has consistently reported lower gender ratios, ranging from 0.50 to 0.94, with the highest ratio of 0.94 observed in 2019-20. This indicates a persistent male dominance in PWD enrollment, with fewer females participating in higher education. West Bengal also exhibits low gender ratios, reaching its lowest point at 0.37 in 2014-15. Although there were slight improvements in subsequent years, with the ratio increasing to 0.74 in 2017-18, it remains below the national average. This reflects ongoing difficulties in achieving gender equality in PWD enrollment. Both Gujarat and West Bengal need to enhance their policies and initiatives to better support and encourage female participation in higher education for PWD students.

Figure 2: State-wise Comparison of Gender Ratios in PWD Enrollment (2012-2022)

Figure 2 depicts a state-wise comparison of the gender ratio in Persons with Disabilities (PWD) enrollment across four states: Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, West Bengal, and Kerala, from the academic year 2012-13 to 2021-22. The gender ratio, represented as a value, compares male and female enrollment. A ratio above 1.0 indicates higher female enrollment, while below 1.0 indicates higher male enrollment.

Uttar Pradesh shows a notable peak around 2015-16, indicating a temporary surge in female enrollment, but fluctuates considerably over time. Gujarat maintains a more stable trend below 1.0, indicating consistent male dominance in enrollment. West Bengal has a relatively steady low ratio, suggesting lower female enrollment, while Kerala shows a mild rise and fluctuation, staying closer to parity compared to other states. Overall, the gender ratio varies significantly across states and over time.

6. CONCLUSION

The analysis of PWD enrollment and gender ratios in higher education across India from 2012-13 to 2021-22 provides several key insights into trends related to inclusion and gender balance. Despite the enactment of the RPWD Act, the overall PWD enrollment ratio remains low, with only gradual increases over the decade. Although the total number of PWD students has risen, the rate of inclusion lags behind the overall expansion of higher education in India.

Gender imbalances are evident in PWD enrollment, with males consistently outnumbering females. This data highlights the need for targeted policies to address barriers specifically affecting female PWD students and to improve gender balance in higher education. Kerala stands out as a leader in PWD inclusion, demonstrating high enrollment ratios and gender parity.

Conversely, states such as Gujarat and West Bengal face challenges with low PWD enrollment and notable gender imbalances. These disparities reflect the uneven implementation of inclusive policies across different regions. The COVID-19 pandemic has adversely affected PWD enrollment, particularly for female students. The decline in both total PWD enrollment and gender parity during 2020-21 indicates that the pandemic exacerbated existing barriers, including difficulties in accessing remote learning and educational resources for PWD students.

The findings underscore the necessity for ongoing efforts to enhance the inclusion of PWD students in higher education, with a particular emphasis on achieving gender parity. Although progress has been made, especially in certain regions, significant challenges remain in attaining full inclusivity and equal representation for PWD students nationwide. To ensure equitable access to higher education opportunities for PWD students, it is crucial to implement targeted policies that address both regional disparities and gender-specific barriers. Such policies are essential for fostering an environment where all PWD students, regardless of gender, can thrive in higher education.

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